

youth
SKILLS

Digital contexts and skills
of Italian Adolescents

Results from the 2nd round of
the ySKILLS survey (2022)

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Abstract

The present report briefly summarizes findings from the first wave of the ySKILLS survey, administered to a sample of 1790 Italian pupils from 8 schools (3 lower secondary and 5 upper secondary) from the Milan area. It first contextualises the research by reporting on children's background, focusing on individual and social characteristics. Then, data on children's daily access to the internet, such as time spent online and devices used are provided. Following, a list of the most and least common online activities children engage in is presented; moving forward we report on Italian children's digital skills across four dimensions (technological and operational, information and navigation, communication and interaction, content creation and production). Finally, we report on the main risks Italian children are exposed to.

When relevant, differences for age and gender are reported.

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This research

The overarching aim of ySKILLS is to enhance and maximise long-term positive impact of the ICT environment on multiple aspects of wellbeing for all children and young people by stimulating resilience through the enhancement of digital skills. In order to achieve this overarching aim, the ySKILLS team seeks to acquire extensive knowledge and better measurement of digital skills in order to contribute to building evidence-based policy. This is done through a three-year longitudinal study conducted with children aged 12-17 in six European countries (Estonia, Finland, Germany, Italy, Poland, and Portugal). The present report briefly summarises findings from the first wave of the ySKILLS survey, administered to a sample of 1790 Italian pupils from 8 schools (3 lower secondary and 5 upper secondary) from the Milan area*.

School grade and gender

How they live: financial comfort

Participants

1790 students from 8 schools

15% Already felt some type of discrimination.

More than 9 in 10 Speak Italian as Mother Tongue.

Know how to deal with problems and new situations

8 in 10 like to explore strange places.

4 in 10 like to do frightening things and prefer friends who are excitingly unpredictable.

4 in 10 consider their health "very good" or "excellent"

Less than 1 in 2 have been physically active daily

Boys are more likely than girls to consider themselves healthy (84% vs. 68%) and to be physically active (55% vs. 35%)

More than 9 in 10 feel supported at home

More than 8 in 10 feel they can count of their friends and that their friends really try to help them when in need

4 in 10 say they like the class environment a lot

*Survey: Mascheroni, G., Helsper, E.J., Schneider, L., van Deursen, A.J.A.M. & van Laar, E. (2021). *youth Digital Skills Indicator. Italian questionnaire*. Developed for ySKILLS project. KU Leuven, Leuven: ySKILLS

Daily access to the internet

Comment on devices use

Although the smartphone is the most widely used device, it is important to emphasise that smartphone access does not bridge all the gaps in digital inclusion. Indeed, while the smartphone may be handy for some activities, it may also hinder others (e.g., the use of educational platforms).

Smartphones are the most popular means to go online thanks to its mobile and personalised nature. However, this does not compensate for potential digital inequalities as smartphone's use is more associated with specific activities (such as communication and entertainment activities) than with others.

Conditions of access

It is noteworthy that 21% of the respondents (2 in 10) reported problems with internet access at least "sometimes".

Domestic internet access increased of 2 points compared to the first ySKILLS survey conducted in 2021. This, however, may be due to the increase in the size of the sample.

Estimated average time online (in hours) on a school day, by gender and school level

Compared to the first wave, the average time spent online increased by 3.4 hours. As in the previous survey, however, the differences in terms of time spent online are not statistically significant either by gender or by school grade.

Daily online activities*

Top 4

96%

communicate with friends.

88%

listen to music or watched videos or music clips online.

83%

communicate with parents or caregivers.

57%

play games on computer or phone.

The most popular activities are easily performed on smartphones

In terms of **gender** differences, **boys** are more likely to play online games than girls (74% vs. 40%)

Older children are more likely to communicate with their parents (85% vs. 74%), communicate with friends (96% vs. 93%) and listen to music or watch videos online (90% vs. 77%)

Consolidate and learning new things

36%

used the internet or phone to learn something new

29%

used the internet or phone to practice something I was learning

Least indicated daily activities

15%

created and edited some digital contents (music, videos, gifs, memes)

12%

look for new friends or contacts.

28%

search or follow news about local, social, environmental or political issues.

10%

search for information about physical health, injury, or physical treatment.

10%

search for information about mental health, mental difficulties, or psychological well-being.

Girls are more likely than boys to search for information on mental health (12% vs. 7%)
Older children are more likely to follow news online (28% vs. 22%), while younger children are more likely to create and edit digital content (25.3% vs. 14%)

Social media use, digital sharing practices and civic participation

Social Media

93% have a profile on social media (Instagram, Facebook, Tik Tok)

84% set their profile to private

8 in 10 accept friend requests from people they have never met at least once face to face.

Girls (94% vs. 91%) and older children are more likely to have a profile on social media (94% vs. 88%)
Girls are more likely to set their profiles private (89% vs. 79%)
Girls (82% vs. 75%) and older children are more likely to accept friend requests from strangers (80% vs. 57%)

Sharing practices

20% shared information or content posted by someone else without asking for their permission.

18% shared some information about themselves with people they had never met face to face before.

6 in 10 publicly shared a photo or a video (e.g., on Instagram) in a way that it could be viewed by people that they have never met face to face before.

Girls (65% vs. 51%) and older children are more likely to share a photo or video of themselves in a way that could be viewed by strangers (60% vs. 40%)

Civic participation

28% joined or followed a political group on social networks.

16% participated in an internet-based protest or campaign.

43% discussed or commented on social or political issues on the internet.

Girls (32% vs. 22%) and older children are more likely to join or follow a political group on social media (29% vs. 19%)

*Activities performed during the last month.

Digital skills

Definition of digital skills:

“In ySKILLS we understand digital skills as a diverse set of operational, information navigation, communicative, and creative competences, which are unequally distributed and influenced by a number of individual and contextual variables.” (d’Haenens & Joris, 2021)

4 digital skills groups

Communication and interaction

Technical and operational

Content creation and production

Information and navigation

Each group includes functional and critical dimensions.

Examples of functional and critical dimension:

I know how to edit existing digital images, music and videos

Functional dimension

I know how to reference and use content covered by copyright

Critical dimension

On average, Italian children report higher levels of communication and interaction skills (62%) and lower levels of information and navigation skills (31%).

Information and navigation skills are important because they are linked to a variety of positive outcomes, including: wider range of online opportunities, higher academic achievements, coping behaviour, civic participation (Livingstone, Mascheroni & Stoilova, 2021).

Digital skills

Differences in skills by school level

Lower secondary school students report higher level of digital skills in every area

Upper Sec
Lower Sec

Differences in skills by gender

These gender differences are in line with those emerged from the first survey in 2021. Again, consistent with prior research, girls tend to report more communication and interaction skills. However, it is important to note that boys tend to overestimate their skills in self-report studies, whereas gender differences are less pronounced when looking at performance test results (Haddon et al., 2020).

Boys
Girls

How students that participated in both waves (674) reported their skills at high level

Communication and interaction skills

Technical and operational skills

Content creation and production skills

Information and navigation skills

Only **technical and operational skills** show a small increase, whereas the other skills have slightly decreased.

Digital knowledge indicators among students who participated in both the first and second wave of the survey

Respondents answered a series of questions designed to measure their knowledge of how the internet and digital technologies work.

The percentage of correct answers concerning the functioning of the internet and digital technologies increased by 4 points - from 46% to 50%.

The percentage of correct answers concerning how the internet and digital technologies work is higher for boys and increases with age.

Risks

Percentage of adolescents who have seen sexual images, sexting, harmful content and cyberhate.

Compared to the first survey, there is a significant **increase in three out of four dimensions** of the risks identified, with an increase from 35% to 56% for sexting, from 54% to 70% for exposure to sexual content, and from 54% to 65% for exposure to harmful and unhealthy content. Boys are more frequently exposed to sexting (49% vs. 37%) and sexual content (82% vs. 57%). All four dimensions investigated are more frequent for older children.

Cyberhate*

feel upset when seeing cyberhate content.

Girls feel significantly more upset than boys by hate content (97% vs. 69% - difference not apparent in the first wave), while no differences emerge with respect to school grade.

74% of girls have been exposed to cyberhate online, compared to 68% of boys.

Differences by school level in exposure to cyberhate.

*With cyberhate we refer to content that attacks certain groups or individuals (e.g., because of their skin colour, religion, nationality, gender, or sexuality).

Harmful content*

feel upset when seeing harmful content.

Again, girls are more likely to feel upset than boys (63% vs. 32%), while no significant differences emerge by school grade.

70% of girls have been exposed to harmful content online, compared to 60% of boys.

Differences by school level in exposure to harmful content

*With harmful content we refer to content (texts, images, videos) that is not healthy or that can be harmful. This includes content about taking drugs, alcohol, harmful and unhealthy dieting or eating, or other behaviour which can be harmful for your health

Cyberbullying

Percentage of adolescents who have been cyberbullied in the last year

As in the first wave, most respondents report not having experienced any cyberbullying in the past year. However, it is important to note that, taking all those who have experienced it together, 3 out of 10 respondents have experienced it at least once, and 2 out of 10 more than once.

Differences by school level and gender

No significant differences emerge in the frequency of cyberbullying incidents either by school grade or gender.

Sec. 1°
grado

Sec. 2°
grado

Maschi

Femmine

Per saperne di più sul progetto, visita: www.yskills.eu